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Research Article

PREFERENTIAL SITES FOR INTRACRANIAL BLEEDING IN PATIENTS WITH HYPERTENSION AND OR DIABETES

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Abstract:

Intracranial hemorrhage is a serious kind of stroke which appears suddenly without giving any warning signs and symptoms. The stroke accounts for 10-15% of the strokes which are spontaneous and it is referred as a bleeding within the intracranial vault¹. The blood may surround the meningeal spaces and brain parenchyma². A report published in USA states intracranial bleeding cases are from 40,000 to 67,000 per annum. The mortality rate is about 35 to 50% in the stated cases in USA and the survivor rate is about 20% in the USA population³.

Mortality rate is high in first 24 hours of the stroke. The risk factor for intracranial bleeding is hypertension (high blood pressure). High blood pressure is considered a silent killer and the less common risk factors are trauma, tumors, and infections, abnormalities in blood vessels and deficiency in blood clotting. Intracranial bleeding may occur at any age group but commonly it is observed in older age group.

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INTRODUCTION:**Intracranial bleeding compartments:**

Intracranial bleeding may occurs either intra axial or extra axial which is described in the table

Table 1

Intra axial bleeding	Extra axial bleeding
Intra parenchyma	Intraventricular
	Epidural or subdural
	Subarachnoid

It is important to locate the position of the bleeding; it will help to identify the cause of bleeding.

Intra Axial Bleeding is also called intra parenchymal hemorrhage take place because of hypertension which can damage the walls of blood vessels.

Extra Axial Bleeding:

The appearance of the subdural hematomas is like biconvex lens and takes place between the skull and the dura mater outer endosteal layer involving the venous sinuses.

The appearance of the epidural hematomas is like the crescent shape and takes place between the arachnoids and dura engaging the bridging veins Subarachnoid appearance is like ruptured arteriovenous irregularity in patients

Chronology of Hemorrhage:

Bleeding chronology can be described from chronic to hyper acute depending upon the time duration from intra cranial bleeding as shown in the table 2

Table 2

Hemorrhage	Time
Hyper acute	More than 12 hours
Acute	From 12 hours to third day
Sub acute early	From third day to week
Sub acute late	From week to one month
Chronic	More than one month

Intracranial hemorrhage Pathology:

In hyper acute stage the vessels ruptures and red blood cells accumulate at the interstitial space and in the acute stage the oxygen of red blood cells shifts to other cells which are adjacent to them. The hemoglobin of the cells oxidize at the early sub acute stage and in the later sub acute stage the red blood cells destruction starts due to the depletion of glucose reserves and at the chronic stage macrophages clear the dead red blood cells

- Trauma
- Tumor hemorrhage
- Ischemic stroke
- Venous hemorrhagic infarct
- Blood clotting abnormalities

Causes of intra cranial bleeding:

Following may be the etiology of the intracranial bleeding

- Intra cranial bleeding is because of hypertension induced and usually occurs after 45 years of age and affects the basal ganglia of deep brain structure
- Intra cerebral bleeding occurs at the lobar region and badly affects the parietal and frontal lobes and is linked with the small or micro bleed. The elder patients are at high risk
- Hematoma are observed due to the vascular malformation in the sub arachnoids bleeding

Diagnostics radiology for the intracranial bleeding:

Mostly the CT scan and MRI are strongly recommended to analyze the severity of the bleeding in the patients.

Results of CT scan in different chronology of bleeding:

The images of CT scan are different according to the bleeding appearances. The images of hyper acute stage are little heterogeneous in appearance with densities normal to the cerebral parenchyma areas which is around 45-60 HU. In early acute and acute stage the density increased up to 80 HU and looks like an edema. The hematoma becomes isodense around area of normal parenchyma in late acute stage. In chronic stage the hypo dense look is surrounded by the brain.

Figure 1 CT images with chronology of hemorrhage

Link: https://posterng.netkey.at/esr/viewing/index.php?module=viewing_poster&task=&pi=119782&searchkey

If the volume of the blood in intracranial area is high then it will enhance the intracranial pressure which may cause

- Changes in the white grey area
- Sulci obliteration
- Shift of midline
- Ventricle ipsilateral compression either without or with the enlargement of contra lateral ventricular

Appearance of Bleeding in MRI:

Bleeding appearance in the MRI is isointense on T1 weighted image and the intensity of signal is high on T2 weighted images in hyper acute stage and in acute stage the low intensity of signal on T2 weighted image and little isointense on T1 weighted image. The signal intensity is high in T1 weighted image and low in T2 weighted image in early acute stage. In late acute stage the signal intensity on T1 and T2 weighted images are high. The chronic stage images show the hemosiderin as hypo intense in T2 weighted image and small hypo intense in T1 weighted image.

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Figure 2 MRI appearances in the chronology of hemorrhage

Difference in both the diagnosis:

Both the techniques are helpful in identifying the hemorrhages and their stages for treatment plan. The weaknesses of the MRI detected hemorrhages are sometimes confused with the conditions or pathologies which can cause hyper intensity on the T1 weighted images for example melanin, protein, lesions having fat and calcification. Hyper intensity may also be because of methemoglobin in T1 weighted images. Dermoids and lipomas also appear hyper intense in T1 weighted images. But using fat suspension techniques the fat can be differentiated from the bleeding. Calcification also appears hypo intense like bleeding which can be differentiated by the location, morphology and by the abnormal signals intensity.

CT scan also helps to differentiate the hypo intensity causes from the hemorrhage. In the CT images the

hemorrhages can be confused from the residual gadolinium linked contrast.

Important factors in Prognosis:

Following are considered the most important factors which are helpful in the prognosis of the intracranial bleeding.

- Intensity of stroke
- Location of bleeding
- Size of bleeding

CONCLUSION:

- CT scan is helpful in identifying the intracranial bleeding but results of MRI are more accurate and sensitive in the chronic and sub acute stage and helpful in providing the information about the complications, location, status of vessels and the size of the ICH (intra cranial Hemorrhage)

- Both the MRI and CT scan can help in the accurate diagnosis of the ICH in the neurological emergency.

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